

A Study to Assess the Level of Awareness and Attitude Regarding Female Foeticide among Antenatal Women Attending Antenatal OPD Services at Selected Hospitals of Moradabad, Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract:- Background: The twenty-first century creates a situation in which women are vulnerable in both the external and internal environments (Mother Womb) around the world. India is the fourth-most dangerous country in the world for women due to the prevalence of human trafficking, infanticide, and female foeticide. **Objectives:** 1. Determine the level of awareness of female foeticide among pregnant women. 2. To determine pregnant women's attitudes towards female foeticide. **Materials and Methods:** A descriptive A cross-sectional investigation was conducted on 150 people pregnant women visiting the antenatal OPD at Teerthanker Mahaveer Hospital and Research Center in Moradabad, Uttar Pradesh. Female foeticide awareness questionnaire's and attitude scale questionnaire's administered to determine the level of awareness and attitude towards female foeticide among pregnant women. Data was analyzed using Statistical Package EZR- software version 2.4. **Results:** The majority of participants (50.7%) have a low level of awareness. The majority of participants (78.0%) oppose female foeticide. **Conclusion:** We can raise awareness and change antenatal women's attitudes towards female foeticide through awareness programmes and campaigns.

Keywords:- Knowledge, Attitude, Female Foeticide, Antenatal Women.

I. INTRODUCTION

The best creatures created by God are man and woman. Both people are equally capable of carrying out all the tasks. Male or female children can only be conceived by females. Lady plays the key roles both inside and outside of the home [1] Approximately 0.59% of expectant women preferred a male child. The sex ratio in the Sangli district, according to the D.H.O, is 840:1000. [2] According to UN data, over 750,000 girls are aborted in India each year. [3] Male child superiority, boy is mad, girl is a financial burden, son looks after parents in their old age, son carries on family name and occupation, and son performs religious ceremonies are all elements that contribute to female foeticide. [4] The reasons behind female foeticides with wishes for the son the hope that boys will provide financially for the family and care for their elderly parents. Because there are so many families believe that The money will not be recovered by the girls invested in their education and marriage, and that they only belong in their husband's home, the dowry system is thought to be one of its primary causes. [5]

II. METHODOLOGY

In order to determine the degree of knowledge and opinions on female foeticide among pregnant women who use the prenatal OPD services at Teerthanker Mahaveer Hospital and Research Centre, Teerthanker Mahaveer University, Moradabad, this research employed a thorough cross-section design. The study was conducted in 2018 between November

and December. The study's sample size was 150 (using the formula sample size estimation of proportion)) by adopting convenient sampling technique.

➤ *Ethical consideration:*

- Approval was obtained from -:
 - Teerthnaker Mahaveer Hospital and Research Center's medical director
 - The Director of Obstetrics and Gynecology at Teethanker Mahaveer Hospital and Research Centre.
 - Subjects provided all of their consent.

➤ *Inclusion criteria:*

- Pregnant women, both primi and multigravida
- Pregnant mothers who can understand and compose in English or Hindi

➤ *Exclusion criteria:*

- Women who are pregnant yet refuse to take part in the study.

➤ *Data collection:*

The following instruments were used in this research to collect data:

- Demographic Performance is the first tool.
- Tool 2: Female foeticide awareness test for pregnant women
- Tool 3: Pregnant women's attitudes towards female foeticide.

III. RESULTS

The data showed that the majority (65.3%) of the sample was between the ages of 18 and 25; the majority (54.7%) of the sample was located in a rural area; 32.0% of the antenatal women had only completed high school; the majority (86.7%) of pregnant women were stay-at-home moms, 22.7% of their partners had graduate degrees, and 26.0% had professional jobs, Almost 64.7% of the sample's members practiced Hinduism, The majority of the sample (34.7%) heard about female foeticide via media, the majority (70.7%) of pregnant women have no preference for kid's gender, and around 68.0% of antenatal women's husbands or relatives have no preference for child.

Table 1 *Frequency and Percentage distribution of samples based on level of awareness* N=150

Level of awareness	f	%
High level of awareness	12	8.0
Moderate level of awareness	62	41.3
Low level of awareness	76	50.7

A low level of awareness is present among the majority of participants (50.7%). Only 8.0% of participants display high consciousness, compared to 41.3% who exhibit moderate awareness.

Table 2 *Frequency and Percentage distribution of samples based on type of attitude* N=150

Type of Attitude	f	%
Unfavorable attitude	117	78.0
Favorable attitude	32	21.3
Neither favorable nor unfavorable attitude	1	0.7

Approximately 21.3% of people have a favorable attitude (against) female foeticide, while the majority (78.0%) have an unfavorable attitude (Supporting) it. Only 0.7% of people have neither a positive nor a negative opinion about female foeticide.

The correlation between the two measures shows an inverse relationship between awareness and attitude towards female foeticide among prenatal women. R has a value of - 0.720. The degree of awareness and attitude had an inverse relationship. (A higher awareness number indicates a more positive attitude towards female foeticide.

IV. DISCUSSION

According to the findings of the current study, most participants (50.7%) have a low level of awareness. Only 8.0% of those surveyed reported being highly informed.

According to the current study, which was According to Singh et al.'s (2015) study, the majority of them (87%) were aware of female foeticide. Female foeticide was made known to approximately (47.4%) of the population through instructors, dramas, and other methods. The authors proposed that this topic be incorporated in school curricula to create awareness throughout the country. [6].

According to The majority (78.0%) of participants in the current survey have a negative opinion towards female foeticide, whereas 21.3% have a positive attitude.

According to The majority (57%) of prenatal women responded to the current survey, which was supported by a study done by Nithin et al. (2014) have a negative opinion of female foeticide. Most participants are prepared for sex determination, indicating the need for increased legal punishment knowledge and strict adherence to the PNDDT act. [7]

V. CONCLUSION

Out of 150 participants, approximately 76 (50.7%) have little knowledge of female foeticide, and roughly 117 (78%) have a negative mindset (are supportive of it).

The current research found that the majority of subjects had a favourable attitude (against) female foeticide and that pregnant women have a low level of awareness of female foeticide. We can raise knowledge and influence prenatal women's attitudes about female foeticide through awareness programmes and campaigns.

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